

A Study on Compliance of Pregnant Women in The Consumption of FE Tablets Based on The Incidence of Anemia in Jayapura Regency

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ABSTRACT

Anemia is a condition in which the number of red blood cells (erythrocytes) present in the blood circulation or hemoglobin mass is reduced, so that they are unable to perform their duties as oxygen carriers throughout the tissues. Worldwide, the prevalence of anemia in pregnant women is 43.9%. In Asia, the prevalence is 49.4%, in Africa, 59.1%, in the Americas, 28.2%, and in Europe, 26.1%. Anemia in pregnancy is responsible for 40% of maternal deaths that occur in developing countries. Purpose of this study is to find out whether pregnant women's compliance with the use of iron tablets correlates with the number of anemia cases that occur in the working area of the health center. Yoka. This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach with a correlation design because the researcher wants to observe the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables through cross-sectional analysis. A total of 116 pregnant women came to the Yoka Health Center to check their pregnancies, and 50 of them answered. The highest number of respondents who did not take medication was 19 people (52.8%), moderate anemia 3 people (8.3%), and non-anemia 14 people (38.9%). 10 people from respondents who adhered to medication had mild anemia (34.5%), and 1 person had severe anemia (7.1) and no anemia 3 people (21.3%). According to the above analysis, with a value of $p = 0.225$ and a correlation value of $r = 0.175$, both variables show a very weak correlation strength. Pregnant women's adherence to fe tablets is not associated with anemia. Conclusions about the effect of iron tablets on anemia during pregnancy.

Keywords: Anemia; Fe tablet consumption compliance

INTRODUCTION

According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health in 2014, there are many factors that can cause anemia during pregnancy, one of which is the lack of iron consumed by mothers every day. As a result, iron tablets are considered effective in preventing anemia caused by iron deficiency in pregnant women. (Christians, 2010). The

loss of red blood cells or hemoglobin during pregnancy is the cause of gestational anemia. If the hemoglobin level in your blood is below normal during pregnancy, it is called anemia, which is below 11 grams per second which reduces the ability of the vital organs of the mother and fetus to transport oxygen. If a pregnant woman suffers from iron deficiency anemia during pregnancy, it can negatively affect both the mother and the fetus. This can increase the risk of maternal and fetal mortality (Lailiyah et al., 2020).

Iron deficiency can lead to anemia, such as a lack of protein and iron from food, problems with intestinal absorption, bleeding either sooner or later, and increased iron needs in pregnant women. Iron tablet consumption, parity, age, education level, and iron foods can also cause anemia. (Omasti et al., 2022). If not treated immediately, the effects of anemia in pregnancy can be fatal. Among them, it can cause bleeding and shock, uterine inertia, old partum, uterine Antonia, and premature partum miscarriage. On the other hand, the effects of anemia on this concept can lead to fetal death in the womb, fetal death at birth, high perinatal death, prematurity, and congenital defects. (Astrina, 2007)

According to the World Health Organization, the body's hemoglobin (Hb) levels of less than 11 grams per deciliter are known as gestational iron deficiency anemia. During pregnancy, people with iron deficiency anemia have adverse consequences for the mother and fetus, as well as an increased risk of maternal and fetal death. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 78% of pregnant women in Indonesia experience anemia, an increase from 48.9% in 2019. The WHO also states that iron deficiency in pregnant women ranges between 35 and 37% and increases with gestational age. The WHO also states that gestational anemia causes maternal mortality in developing countries by about 40%, and the prevalence of anemia in pregnant women worldwide is 41.8%. In Papua Province, the prevalence of anemia is very high. It reached 46% in 2018, 38.6% in 2019, and 34% in 2020. In the Yoka Health Center Working Area, the prevalence of anemia in 2020 was 30.4%, and in 2021 it was 31.5% (Papua Health Office Profile 2021). Pregnant women's compliance with taking iron tablets (Fe) is determined by the amount, method, and frequency of iron tablets consumed daily. Taking 60 mg of iron tablets daily can increase Hb levels to 1 gram per month. But Indonesia has tried to prevent anemia by giving pregnant women ninety iron tablets during pregnancy. However, there is no program and pregnant women do not adhere to the recommendations for the use of iron tablets. Omasti et al., 2022

According to data from the Papua Provincial Health Office, the coverage of iron tablets given to pregnant women in Papua Province in 2019 was 63.5% iron tablets -1 and 3rd iron tablets were 42.2%. For data per district and city, the highest is Jayapura Regency at 96.6% and Jayapura City at 83.9%. An initial study at the Yoka Health Center showed that four pregnant women, of which two were pregnant women, complied with the use of iron tablets recommended by the health center; However, two people who were anemic stated that they did not comply with the recommendations of the health center.

The study in question is "The Relationship of Compliance of Pregnant Women in the Consumption of Fe Tablets to the Incidence of Anemia at the Yoka Health Center", based on the information above.

METHOD

The researcher wanted to see how the cross-sectional method was used to determine the relationship between independent and dependent variables, so a quantitative descriptive approach with a correlation design was used. This study was conducted from May to June 2024 at the Yoka Health Center in Heram District, Jayapura City.

A total of 116 pregnant women came to the Yoka Health Center to check their pregnancies. Using the unexpected sample method to determine the number of samples and find the number of fifty people. Data was collected from respondents through questionnaire sheets. In this study, univariate and bivariate analysis was used; bivariate data presentation was evaluated using Spearman's ranking in frequency distribution tabulation and cross tabulation.

RESULT

The result of this study can we see below: **Table 4.1.** Distribution of frequency characteristics of respondents in the Working Area of the Hebe, Yoka Health Center, Heram District, Jayapura City May-June 2024.

Characteristic	Frequency	Presented
Mother's age		
Risk (< 20 & > 30 yrs)	51	22
No risk (20 – 30 yrs)	39	78
Sum	50	100
Education		
Not in school	0	0
Elementary	0	0
Junior School	2	4
High School	29	58
College	19	38
Sum	50	100
Work		
Government worker	15	30
House Wife	31	62
Self employed	1	2
Private	0	0
Police/TNI	3	6
Total	50	100
Income		
1. Good ($\geq$ UMR IDR 4,024,270)	23	46
2. Less (<UMR)	27	54
Total	50	100
Ante Natal Care		
Orderly	2	40
Irregular	48	96
Total	50	100
Gestational Age		
Trimester I	22	44
Trimester II	26	52
Trimester III	2	4
Total	50	100
Parity		
Primipara	20	40

Multipara	30	60
Ante Natal Care	50	100

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on **Tablet 4.1** above, of the 50 people surveyed, 78% were between the ages of 20 and 30, 39 people (78.0%), and 22 people (22.0%) were between the ages of 20 and 30. Of the 50 people surveyed, the most have a high school education level of 58.0%, tertiary education 38.0%, and a junior high school minority of 2 people (4.0%). Of the 50 people surveyed, the most had a junior high school education level of 2 people (4.0%).

FE TABLET CONSUMPTION COMPLIANCE

Table 4.2 Distribution of compliance of pregnant women consuming Fe tablets at the Yoka Health Center

Fe Tablet Consumption Compliance	Frequency	Presented
Obedient	14	28.00%
Non-compliant	36	72.00%
Sum	50	100.00%

Source: Primary Data, 2024

Based on **table 4.2**, it can be seen that from 50 respondents, the majority of non-compliant Fe tablets consumed 36 (72.0) and the minority who adhered to Fe tablet consumption as many as 14 (28.0%).

INCIDENCE OF ANEMIA

Table 4.3 Distribution of Anemia Frequency in the Working Area of Yoka Health Center

Anemia	Frequency	Presented
Mild Anemia	0	0
Moderate Anemia	29	58,0%
Severe Anemia	4	8,0%
No Anemia	17	34,0%
Sum	50	100,0%

Source: Secondary Data, 2024 of the 50 respondents, the majority of pregnant women who experienced moderate anemia were 29 (58.0%), none 17 (34.0%), and the minority of pregnant women who experienced severe anemia was 4 (8.0%).

BIVARIATE ANALYSIS

The Relationship of Compliance of Pregnant Women in the Consumption of Fe Tablets to the Incidence of Anemia

Table. 4.4 Correlation test between the incidence of anemia in pregnant women who have received Fe tablets at the Yoka Health Center

Fe Tablet Consumption Compliance	Incidence of Anemia in Pregnant Women							Total	P-Value	R
	Moderate Anemia		Severe Anemia		No Anemia					
	N	%	N	%	N	%				
Obedient	10	34,5%	1	7,1%	3	21,3%	14	0,225	0,175	
Non-Compliance	19	52,8%	3	8,3%	14	38,9%	36			

Table 4.4 The results show that respondents who do not comply with taking the most medications have moderate anemia (19 people, 52.8%), severe anemia (3 people, 8.3%), and no anemia (14 people, 38.9%). Respondents who adhered to medication also had mild anemia 10 people (34.5%), severe anemia 1 person (7.1), and no anemia 3 people (21.3%). The results of the analysis showed that there was no significant correlation between pregnant women's adherence to the use of iron tablets and the number of anemias that occurred. The correlation strength level was very weak, with a value of $p = 0.225$ (greater than 0.5) and a correlation value of $r = 0.175$. This suggests that, although the consumption of iron tablets by pregnant women does not cause anemia, the observance of pregnant women to the consumption of iron tablets does not cause anemia has a considerable impact on anemia.

DISCUSSION

AGE

At the Yoka Health Center, 39 people (78.0%) were between the ages of 20 and 30 years, and at least 11 people (22.0%) were between the ages of 20 and 30. Increasing a person's age will result in many changes that occur in him (*Wibowo and Purnamasari, 2019*). There are often physical and psychological changes, such as the age at which this age is the reproductive age and often there is a problem, emotional change, adjustment in a new life (*Anggasari et al.*). A previous study by *Amini, Pamungkas, and Harahap (2018)* found that there was a correlation between the age of pregnant women and the number of anemia cases. The results of the statistical research showed a p-value of 0.07, which is a value below 0.05. This is contrary to Wintrobe's opinion, which states that the mother's age can affect the onset of anemia, that is, hemoglobin levels increase with the age of the pregnant woman.

This study shows that age is one of the causes of pregnancy anemia. By the age of twenty to thirty, the reproductive organs have begun to function properly and the mother can safely accept pregnancy and childbirth. Mothers under the age of twenty are at risk of breech lettuce delivery due to the condition of the narrow pelvis, which leads to labor difficulties. In mothers over the age of thirty, regeneration of body cells begins to occur, especially for the endometrium due to the age of tissues and diseases that can cause abnormalities

EDUCATION

At the Yoka Health Center, pregnant women who experience anemia are mostly educated in high school (29 people, or 58.0%), followed by college (19 people, or 38.0%), according to this study. The lowest respondents were 2 people (4.0%). This is in line with the theory that health education aims to make people know how to take care of their own health and that of others, where they can get treatment, and so on. In terms of the choice of food that a person consumes, educational factors can affect his anemia status.

This is in line with [Zuiatna \(2021\)](#) research, which found that the highest education rate in high school is 52.8%, while elementary school is only 7.5%. The results of this study are also in line with the research of [Chandra, Junita, and Fatmawati \(2019\)](#), which found that of the 41 respondents, the majority in secondary school was 28 people (68.3%), junior high school was 10 people (24.4%), and college was 3 people (7.3%).

The above data shows that education also has a significant influence on a person's behavior in a positive direction and is closely related to their knowledge of what they need. Especially for pregnant women, education has a significant influence on their understanding of how to live a healthy and clean life.

INCOME

The results of this study showed that respondents with an income level less than UMR had a higher percentage of 27 people (54.0%), while respondents with a high UMR income level were 23 people (46.0%). This is in line with the research of [Dewi & Mardiana \(2017\)](#), which found that anemia is more common in pregnant women with low economic levels (72.6%) than pregnant women with high economic levels (27.4%). Pregnant women who have low family incomes are unable to meet their nutritional needs during pregnancy, which is at risk of developing anemia. However, another theory says that even if a person has poor economic status but good knowledge of the respondents, anemia will not occur because the respondents know what to eat pregnant women to meet their nutritional needs.

ANTE NATAL CARE

Pregnant women with low economic levels (72.6%) experience anemia more often than pregnant women with high economic levels (27.4%). 48 (96.0%) more than compliant pregnant women by 2 (40.0%). The implementation of ante natal care is very important because it can describe the condition of pregnant women, fetuses and pregnancy health in general. Pregnant women who regularly receive prenatal care will reduce the risk of developing anemia ([Nurhaidah & Rostinah, 2021](#)).

This is in line with research conducted by [Gazali, Arifin, and Hayatie \(2020\)](#), which found that pregnant women with poor antenatal care factors were less likely to develop anemia, with 12 of them experiencing anemia, while pregnant women with adverse antenatal care factors were less likely to experience anemia, with only 1 person (2.6%) experiencing anemia.

GESTATIONAL AGE

The results showed that most of the respondents were in the second trimester (about 26 people, or 52.0%), the first trimester (about 22 people, or 44.0%), and the third trimester (about 2 people, or 4.0%). The results showed

that most of the respondents were in the second trimester (about 26 people, or 52.0%), the first trimester (about 22 people, or 44.0%), and the third trimester (about 2 people, or 4.0%). From the research data, the majority of respondents are in the first trimester of pregnancy, which of course has an impact on the health of pregnant women. This is because women of young gestational age are usually more susceptible to anemia, which results in decreased hemoglobin levels, but there is no theory explaining the relationship between gestational age and the likelihood of anemia in pregnant women.

PARITY

According to the results of the study, most of the pregnant women studied were at primiparity, consisting of twenty people (40 percent), or multipara parity, consisting of thirty people (60 percent). Parity, according to [Ekowati \(2007\)](#), is defined as the number of babies born to living mothers and deceased mothers. The number of mothers who give birth is lower than one child. [Amirudin's \(2010\)](#) study also looked at patients who experienced anemia during pregnancy in 2009 at H.A Sultan Daeng Raja Hospital, Bulukumba Regency. High parity, or 4 children, has a 1,454 times greater risk than low parity to develop anemia, according to the study. The majority of pregnant women in this demographic group are first-time pregnant and giving birth, so they usually have difficulty adjusting to pregnancy because they don't know much or have experience about this issue. about pregnancy compared to women in higher demographic groups.

COMPLIANCE

50 pregnant women who suffered from anemia, only 28.0% took iron tablets and 36 (72.0%) did not comply. During pregnancy, pregnant women consume ninety iron tablets. However, the amount of iron needed by babies and mothers cannot be met through the food they consume. Iron deficiency endangers the growth of the fetus and child. However, anemia will not occur if pregnant women comply with the use of iron tablets. Research conducted by [Adi Lestari W. et al. \(2016\)](#) found that there was a relationship between pregnant women's compliance with the use of iron tablets and a low level of relationship closeness. This discovery is comparable to the results of this study. Pregnant women should drink nutritious regularly because Fe tablets can increase hemoglobin levels. Regular consumption of iron tablets will reduce the risk of anemia in pregnant women.

ANEMIA

Most of the respondents in this study experienced anemia. Medium, namely 29 people (58.0%), compared to 8 people (8.0%) who experienced severe anemia, and 17 people who did not experience anemia (34.0%). In accordance with the theory that the normal hemoglobin concentration of pregnant women is different from that of non-pregnant women, with the normal hemoglobin concentration of pregnant women being 11 grams. This is because blood thinning, or hemodilution, that occurs during pregnancy increases the volume of plasma greater than erythrocytes. According to the data above, most of the people surveyed had moderate or severe anemia, which means that the hemoglobin level of pregnant women is less than 11 grams. However, not taking iron tablets regularly and avoiding foods containing iron are dangerous for pregnancy.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

At the time of the study, some people refused to be respondents, so it required an extension of the research time.

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